

Research Outputs and Open Access Bill 2025, DRAFT [Version 5, February 2025]

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Title	Research Outputs and Open Access Bill 2025 [Draft Version 5, February 2025]			
Description	<p>The SCOIR project is two-year project (2023-2025) funded by the National Open Research Forum (NORF). SCOIR aims to support the goal of 100% open access to publicly-funded research publications by adopting a two-pronged approach to policy and legislative change:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Develop a secondary publishing right for Ireland, drafting legislation in support of secondary publication rights based on an analysis of international and Irish law.2. Develop an open access policy framework for both funders and institutions that is aligned with the National Action Plan for Open Research and international best practice. <p>The project is jointly led by Trinity College Dublin and Technological University Dublin and is supported by a consortium of a wide range of partners and affiliates along with an international advisory board.</p> <p>This document is a draft outcome of (1) above and is subject to revision and a consultation process.</p>			
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Rialtas na hÉireann
Government of Ireland

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Vindicating Research Outputs.

Achieving the goals of Secondary Publishing Rights and Rights Retention in Ireland by means of a

draft Research Outputs and Open Access Bill 2025.

Prepared by the **SCOIR Research Group**; funded by **NORF** and **KR21**.¹

Background: The aim of this *draft* Bill is to underpin and vindicate the rights of researchers and their employers and funders to publish publicly-funded research outputs on open access platforms.

Open access publication makes research outputs available for everyone to access, use and re-use. For example, researchers can easily build upon open access publications, to extend their fields, generate novel insights, and make important breakthroughs. More specifically, open access publication ensures greater exposure for publicly funded research, so that other researchers, practitioners, policy-makers, innovators, and members of the public (especially those in developing countries who cannot otherwise afford to access) have easy access to the latest research. This will improve ongoing research, encourage collaboration between researchers, result in higher citation rates for and raise the profiles of (in our case, Irish) researchers internationally, facilitate public engagement and education, and help to guide public policy. It will preserve important research material, lead to new knowledge and greater innovation, and ensure that taxpayers get full value for the public money invested in research. And it will help to meet the current Government policy of strengthening support for open research,² in particular by achieving 100% open access to research publications by 2030.³ As Simon Harris TD, then Minister for Further and Higher Education, Research Innovation and Science, wrote in 2022:⁴

¹ **SCOIR** Research Group: the **S**econdary rights, **C**opyright, **O**pen access, **I**nstitutional policies, and **R**ights retention Research Group; consisting of Prof Eoin O’Dell (TCD), Frances Madden (TUD), Niamh Brennan (TCD), Kaberi Basu (TCD) and Arushi Sharma (TCD); <https://scoir.moodlecloud.com>

NORF: the **N**ational **O**pen **R**esearch **F**orum; <https://norf.ie>

KR21: **K**nowledge **R**ights **21**; <https://www.knowledgerights21.org>

² *2030: Ireland’s Research and Innovation Strategy* (2022) pp28, 54.

³ *National Action Plan for Open Research 2022-2030* (2022) pp12-16.

⁴ In the Introduction to the *Action Plan*, p2.

The international movement towards greater openness and transparency in research sets new expectations for research to be open, collaborative and shared for the benefit of science and society. ... Progress on this agenda will increase the visibility of Irish research and support research excellence and impact ... [and] enable the open sharing of knowledge and the re-use of research outputs.

The Bill is an important means of meeting these objectives. It removes any legal ambiguity with making publicly-funded research outputs available on open access platforms, and it provides a solid legal basis for workflows to do so.

The rights of researchers and their employers and funders to publish publicly-funded research outputs on open access platforms are often cast in the language of copyright exceptions, secondary publishing rights and retained rights. The approach in this draft Bill is slightly different. It does not propose secondary publishing rights and/or retained rights *in those terms*. Instead, the Bill builds on distinctions and definitions in existing legislation to provide a workflow that operates outside the scope of existing copyright legislation. That workflow consists of an obligation on authors' employers, and entitlements for authors and funders, to make publicly funded research outputs available to the public by means of an open repository. This relatively short Bill tries to avoid too much detail and technicality, the better to understand and adopt the solutions proposed here. In this way, research outputs are vindicated, and the goals of secondary publishing rights and rights retention are achieved in Ireland, without disturbing the balances in existing copyright legislation.

Section 1, on short title and commencement, is a standard clause.

Section 2, on definitions, integrates this Bill with previous legislation (including the Copyright and Related Rights Act, 2000 [CRRRA], the European Union (Open Data and Re-use of Public Sector Information) Regulations 2021 (S.I. No. 376/2021) [2021 Regulations], and the Higher Education Authority Act 2022); and it then provides additional definitions necessary for the Bill itself. For ease of reference, the main relevant provisions of the pieces of legislation to which the Bill refers are set out at the end of this document, after the text of the draft Bill.

The key provision in the Bill is section 4(2). It includes:

- an obligation on the employers of authors to make publicly funded research outputs available to the public by means of an open repository (section 4(2)(a)),
- an entitlement on the employers of joint authors to do so (section 4(2)(b)),
- an entitlement of authors, joint authors and funders to do so (section 4(2)(c)), and
- an entitlement of authors, joint authors, employers and funders to make works similarly available (section 4(2)(d)).

The building blocks of that provision are defined in section 2.

A key concept in section 4(2) is the "author" of the relevant work. Section 21 CRRA provides for interpretation of author for the purposes of copyright, and that definition is adopted and supplemented in this Bill. Section 22 CRRA provides for "works of joint authorship", and that concept too is adopted in this Bill. Section 23 CRRA provides for first ownership of copyright, and this Bill does not amend or affect that in any way. Moreover, this Bill builds on the distinction between author and first owner of copyright inherent in sections 21 and 22 CRRA, on the one hand, and section 23 of the Act, on the other; it utilizes the former without disturbing the latter. There are two additions to the definition of author. It extends to a creator of a publicly funded artistic work, and a performer of a qualifying performance; this ensures that, where such a creator or performer intends the work to constitute a research output, the obligations and entitlements in section 4 will apply.

Another key concept in section 4(2) is the relevant "work". Again, the definition in CRRA is adopted, and again it supplemented to include creators' artistic works, and performers' qualifying performances.

Among the several new definitions in section 2 are definitions of "open repository" and research "outputs". The former is derived from international best practice. For the latter, the definition of "research" in the Research and Innovation Act 2024 is adopted here. That provides that research "means creative and systematic work in any discipline that is undertaken in order to increase the stock of knowledge (including knowledge of humankind, culture and society) and to devise new applications of available knowledge". The definition of "output" is added here; it builds upon the definition of "work" already described above; it includes artistic works, and performances; and it turns not only upon (a) the academic context in which the relevant work is

produced, but also upon (b) the intention of the author that the relevant work primarily furthers such academic purposes or interests.

On the one hand, this means that the definition of research output for the purposes of the obligation in section 4(2) is relatively broad. In particular, it means that where the author of a non-traditional research output intends that output to be a research output for the purposes of the Bill, then the obligations in section 4(2) will apply.

On the other hand, though broad, there are clear limits to this definition. In particular, it means that outputs that are not intended primarily to be research outputs are expressly excluded from the obligations in section 4(2). For example, publicly funded artistic works supported by Arts funders or produced by artists- or writers-in-residence do not amount to "research" as defined in the Research and Innovation Act 2024, and are not "outputs" primarily intended to further academic purposes or interests. Such works are therefore not within the definition of "research outputs" that emerges from section 2, and are thus not subject to the obligations in section 4 that research outputs should be made available in an open repository. This is reinforced by the specific treatment of publicly funded artistic works in section 5.

"Publicly funded" is referred to but not defined in the 2021 Regulations; and that lead (of leaving the term undefined) is followed here. To be clear, the phrase must be understood as expansively as possible. Hence, it includes not only specific grant funding but also public funding by means of salaries, contracts, and the like. This is the position in the application of the 2021 Regulations, and it will be the position here too.

Section 3, on regulations and orders, is largely a standard clause, except for the addition of subsection (3). That new subsection provides two important safety valves.

First, the line between research outputs to which the obligations in section 4(2) apply, and other works to which the obligations in section 4(2) do not apply, may prove difficult to draw in practice; and it may be that some cases may arise where this definition is unnecessarily over- or under-inclusive. To address this concern, section 3(3) permits the Minister to provide any necessary additional qualification to this definition of "output", provided that any such qualification is consistent with the purpose and substance of section 4.

Second, to ensure that the obligations in section 4 do not go too far, section 5 provides for an exclusion for publicly funded artistic works, and section 6 provides exceptions, limitations and postponements. To ensure that they can be kept up to date, section 3(3) also permits the Minister to provide any necessary additional exclusions exceptions, limitations, and postponements, provided again that they are consistent with the purpose and substance of section 4.

Section 4, on making research outputs available, is the heart of the Bill.

Recall that "research" and "outputs" are carefully defined in section 2.

Subsection (1) provides that sections 21, 22 and 23 CRRA (on authors, joint authors, and first owners of copyright) will not prevent the operation of this section, that the operation of the Bill is without prejudice to the operation of section 23 CRRA (on first owners of copyright), and – following the lead of section 2(10) CRRA – that contractual clauses that seek to exclude the rights conferred by the Bill are void.

Subsection (2) is the key provision in the Bill. Subsection (2)(a) requires that employers of authors must make publicly-funded research outputs available to the public by means of an open repository. This effectively incentivises employers to develop workflows to encourage and support authors in making their research outputs available by means of an open repository. And there are at least two workflows by which the employer can meet this obligation. First, the employer can do so by means of its own repository (many academic institutions already have their own open access repositories). In this way, the employer will "make ... the research output available to the public by means of an open repository". Second, the employer can do so by making an arrangement with an external repository (many funders have suitable repositories, and there are important independent repositories as well). In this way, the employer will "cause to make the research output available to the public by means of an open repository". Either workflow will discharge the obligation in subsection (2)(a).

Subsection 2(b) provides that the employers of any joint authors may (also) make that research output similarly available; and subsection 2(c) provides that joint authors or funders may (also) make that research output similarly

available. In both of these cases, this will discharge the obligation in subsection (2)(a).

Subsection 2(d) provides that, in the case of any research output or other work not within the obligation in subsection 2(a), the author, employer or funder can still take advantage of the workflows put in place to meet that obligation to make that other output or work available to the public by means of an open repository. For example, some matters may be regarded as research outputs by one relevant employer but not by another. Where it is regarded as a research output, then the employer will have an obligation to make or to cause to make it available pursuant to subsection 2(a). But, even if the employer does not regard it as a research output covered by the obligation in subsection 2(a), the employee can take advantage of the workflow put in place for those purposes to make it available pursuant to subsection 2(d).

Subsection 2(a) is the principal obligation on employers in section 4. But there is a second important obligation. Subsection 2(e) imposes an additional obligation that, where a research output has been accepted for publication by a publisher but has not already been made available pursuant to paragraph (a), then the employer must ensure that the author immediately deposits that output in an appropriate open repository.

Subsection (3) provides for similar obligations and entitlements where an author or joint author is self-employed. Following international best practice, subsection (4) provides for use or reuse for any lawful purpose; subsection (5) provides for digital object identifiers and metadata, and subsection (6) requires that research outputs published in open repositories be "interoperable". This concept is referred to but not defined in several Acts and statutory instruments (see, in particular, the European Union (Electronic Communications Code) Regulations 2022 (S.I. No. 444/2022) where the interoperability of services is a key obligation of service providers); and that lead (of leaving the term undefined) is followed here.

Subsection (6) also follows the lead provided by the 2021 Regulations, in particular by providing for an open public licence on foot of which research outputs and other works deposited in an open repository can be made available. In the context of the re-use of public sector data, at present, the recommended licence is Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY) 4.0 (see Department of Public Expenditure and Reform Circular 12/2016). That licence is adopted in this Bill, and research outputs and other works deposited in an

open repository can be made available on foot of it, where that is practicable and appropriate. However, if another licence (such as another Creative Commons licence, or another generally-available open public licence, or a bespoke open public licence) is more appropriate, that may be used instead. Moreover (and, again, following the lead from the 2021 Regulations) whatever licence is appropriate, subsection (8) acknowledges that additional conditions may be imposed, provided that they are necessary.

Subsection (7) seeks to ensure that research outputs or other works made available by an open repository are accessible to persons with a disability. In particular, for the purposes of such access, section 104B(2) CRAA provides that the electronic form of the relevant work shall enable copies of the work to be made

- (a) without undue difficulty,
- (b) which are easily navigated, and
- (c) which are capable of being modified.

And that requirement is incorporated by this subsection into the Bill, to ensure that research outputs made available by an open repository are accessible to persons with a disability.

Subsection (8) requires that the open repository must make the research outputs or other works available without charge (reinforcing the same point made in the definition in section 2), and not subject to unnecessary conditions. Subsection (9) provides that authors, employers or funders may also make research outputs or other works available in any other location. Subsection (10) ensures that research outputs or other works that have been made available by an open repository should remain freely available in perpetuity. And subsection (11) provides for sufficient acknowledgement of the author, the repository, and the location of its first publication by a publisher.

Note that the "publisher" referred to here in subsection 10, as well as in subsection (2)(e) above, is the "publisher" referred to in section 21 CRRRA. However, that term is not defined in that Act; and that lead (of leaving the term undefined) is followed here.

Section 5 explains when publicly funded artistic works are excluded from the obligations in section 4(2), even where the work may have been created in an educational or research institution. Publicly funded artistic works are defined

in section 2 as artistic works funded for wholly or mainly artistic purposes by public funding bodies such as the Arts Council.

Section 6 provides for exceptions to, limitations upon, and postponements of, the obligations and entitlements in section 4.

Subsection (1) provides that, by way of exception to section 4, the obligation to make research outputs available by an open repository does not apply in various contexts, as where publication is precluded by another legal rule (such as national security or the GDPR), or where the content of the output is a protected trade secret or patent.

Subsection (2) explains the extent to which intellectual property rights held by third parties provide limitations upon the obligations and entitlements in section 4. As a consequence, the version of the research output published pursuant to section 4 is not the version published by publishers in which they have copyright, unless they have provided a licence to the author for such publication. Instead, it is an earlier version of the manuscript created the author, in respect of which publishers have no intellectual property or other similar rights. This effectively permits the author's accepted manuscript to be made available by an open repository.

Subsection (3) acknowledges that, where a research output or other work is being deposited in an open repository pursuant to section 4, there may be an imperative reason of overriding public interest (such as, for example, academic freedom, the legitimate academic interests of the author, or the exceptional nature of a significant and substantial research output) that permits the making available of the output or work to be postponed, but only for so long as is strictly necessary to satisfy that public interest.

Section 7 amends section 288 CRRA, to ensure that the definition of "qualifying performance" can be fully included in the definition of "work" in section 2 of the Bill on which the definition of research "output" is constructed.

Section 8 provides for oversight pursuant to the Higher Education Authority Act 2022.

Section 9 envisages compliance mechanisms pursuant to the Research and Innovation Act 2024, and by other research funding bodies defined in section 2 to include the Health Research Board and Teagasc.

Section 10 permits enforcement by the Ombudsman.

Conclusion: The Bill meets international best practice under a wide range of headings. This is reflected, for example, in the definition of open repository, and in the balance between, on the one hand, the obligations and entitlements in section 4 (which ensure that publicly-funded research is as open as possible), and, on the other, the exclusions, exceptions, limitations and postponements in sections 5 and 6 (which permits publicly-funded research is as closed as necessary). In particular, under the Bill, publicly funded research outputs and other works are findable (because they are made available, pursuant to section 4(2), in an open repository as defined in section 2), accessible (because they are made available in an open format on foot of an open public licence, pursuant to section 4(6)(b)&(c)), interoperable (pursuant to section 4(6)(a)), and reusable (pursuant to an open public licence (section 4(6)(c)) for free, for any lawful purpose (section 4(4)), and not subject to conditions (section 4(8)).

The philosophy behind the Bill is that making publicly-funded research outputs available should be open by design and by default. The subject-matter of the Bill ("research outputs" and other works, in section 4) is as wide as possible (having regard to sections 5 and 6). It encourages immediate publication of the research output (especially having regard to section 4(2)(e) and 4(3)(f), which require that a research output that has been accepted for publication by a publisher but has not already been made available must be immediately deposited in an appropriate open repository). There is no formal or automatic embargo period, but the limited postponement of publication in the public interest (section 6(3)) can achieve a similar purpose on a case-by-case basis. Sections 4(4) (use and re-use for any lawful purpose), 4(9) (republication), 4(6)(c) (open licence), and 4(4), 4(8)& 4(11) (use and re-use, free of charge, with acknowledgement) encourage wide subsequent re-use and publication of research outputs or other works that have been made available in an open repository.

The obligations in section 4 are binding. They do not affect publishers' copyrights in the publication, and apply regardless of them, because the workflow applies to versions of the work that were created before publishers' copyrights subsequently enter the picture. And section 4(1)(d) provides that authors and their employers and funders cannot contract out of section 4.

The Bill currently consists of three Parts. Further Parts can be added to provide for additional or related matters that arise in the course of the ongoing work of the SCOIR Research Group, of other NORF projects, or of cognate aspects of Government policy, that require legislative support.

The publication of this draft Bill marks a pivotal step toward ensuring open access to major research outputs produced by researchers and academics at Irish institutions. By proposing legal frameworks that prioritise transparency and accessibility, this draft Bill is set to transform how research is shared and utilised.

Finally, this is a draft; it still a draft, and still *ONLY a draft*. It contains ideas and principles to achieve the goal of underpinning and vindicating the rights of researchers and their employers and funders to publish publicly-funded research outputs on open access platforms. It is intended for discussion, and it will doubtless have to be edited, amended, added to, subtracted from, corrected, or revised. Any and all comments are encouraged and welcomed.

An Bille Aschuir Thaighde agus Rochtain Oscailte 2025
Research Outputs and Open Access Bill 2025

Mar a tionscnaíodh
As initiated

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An Bille Aschuir Thaighde agus Rochtain Oscailte 2025
Research Outputs and Open Access Bill 2025

BILL

entitled

AN ACT TO ENSURE THE MAKING AVAILABLE OF PUBLICLY FUNDED RESEARCH
OUTPUTS IN OPEN REPOSITORIES, AND TO MAKE PROVISION FOR RELATED
MATTERS.

Be it enacted by the Oireachtas as follows:

PART I

Preliminary and General

1. Short title and commencement.

- (1) This Act may be cited as the Research Outputs and Open Access Act 2025.
- (2) This Act shall come into operation on such day or days as the Minister may by order or orders either generally or with reference to any particular purpose or provision appoint, and different days may be so appointed for different purposes or different provisions of this Act.

2. Interpretation.

- (1) In this Act, unless the context otherwise requires—
"Act of 1980" means the Ombudsman Act, 1980;
"Act of 1997" means the Universities Act, 1997;

"Act of 2000" means the Copyright and Related Rights Act, 2000;

"Act of 2003" means the Arts Act, 2003;

"Act of 2012" means the Qualifications and Quality Assurance (Education and Training) Act 2012;

"Act of 2019" means the Copyright and Other Intellectual Property Law Provisions Act 2019;

"Act of 2022" means the Higher Education Authority Act 2022;

"Act of 2024" means the Research and Innovation Act 2024;

"arts" has the meaning assigned to it in section 2 of the Act of 2003, and "artistic" and cognate words shall be construed accordingly;

"author" has the meaning assigned to it in section 21 of the Act of 2000, whether or not he or she is the first owner of copyright for the purposes of section 23 of the Act of 2000, and includes—

- (a) a creator of a publicly funded artistic work, and
- (b) a performer of a qualifying performance;

"commercially sensitive information" has the meaning assigned to it in section 36(1) of the Freedom of Information Act 2014;

"digital object identifier" is a persistent unique identification as provided for by the International Organization for Standardization in ISO 26324:2022(en) (Information and Documentation — Digital Object Identifier System) or in any replacement document;

"Directive 2001/29/EC" means Directive 2001/29/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 May 2001 on the harmonisation of certain aspects of copyright and related rights in the information society (OJ L 167, 22.6.2001, p. 10–19);

"Foras na Gaeilge" means the Irish language agency established by An Foras Teanga pursuant to the Agreement between the Government of Ireland and the Government of the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland establishing Implementation Bodies done at Dublin on the 8th day of March, 1999, the text of which is set out in the Schedule to the Act of 1999, and to the Act of 1999;

"higher education provider" has the meaning assigned to it in section 2 of the Act of 2022;

"innovation" has the meaning assigned to it in section 2 of the Act of 2024, and subsection (2) of that section shall apply;

"joint authorship" has the meaning assigned to it in section 22 of the Act of 2000; provided that—

- (a) references to "joint authors" shall be construed accordingly,
- (b) for the avoidance of doubt, subsection 2(8) of the Act of 2000 shall apply, and
- (c) this paragraph shall apply whether or not any or some or all of the joint authors is or are the first owner or owners of copyright for the purposes of section 23 of the Act of 2000;

"make available" has the same meaning as in Article 3 of the Directive 2001/29/EC and in sections 40 and 205 of the Act of 2000, and "made available" and cognate words and phrases shall be construed accordingly;

"Minister" means the Minister for Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science;

"open repository" means a robust, sustainable, trusted, online storage and retrieval platform where research outputs and other works are—

- (a) stored and preserved, without charge to the party depositing the research output or other work, and
- (b) made available to the public without charge;

"outputs", subject to section 3(3), includes works that are—

- (a) produced in academic, educational, innovation, intellectual, research, scholarly, scientific, technical, or other similar, contexts, and
- (b) intended by their author or joint authors primarily to further such purposes or interests;

"provider" has the meaning assigned to it in section 2 of the Act of 2012, and "education provider" shall be construed accordingly; provided that "higher education provider" shall be construed according to this section;

"public artistic funding body" means a public body, charity, company, institution or organisation the functions, objects or priorities of which include the funding, development or promotion of artistic activities, and includes—

- (a) the Arts Council, established by the Act of 2003,
- (b) Foras na Gaeilge, and
- (c) funding initiatives of the Department of Tourism, Culture, Arts, Gaeltacht, Sport and Media;

"public research funding body" means a public body, charity, company, institution or organisation the functions, objects or priorities of which

include the funding, development or promotion of research, and includes—

- (a) the Environmental Protection Agency, established by the Environmental Protection Agency Act, 1992,
- (b) the Health Research Board, established by Regulation 2 of the Health Research Board (Establishment) Order 1986 (S.I. No. 279 of 1986) pursuant to section 3 of the Health (Corporate Bodies) Act, 1961,
- (c) the Irish National Meteorological Service, Met Éireann, a division of the Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage, pursuant to the Meteorological Services, Radiological Protection and Nuclear Safety (Transfer of Departmental Administration and Ministerial Functions) Order 2002 (S.I. No. 303 of 2002) as amended by the Housing, Planning and Local Government (Alteration of Name of Department and Title of Minister) Order 2020 (S.I. No. 408 of 2020),
- (d) the Marine Institute, Foras na Mara, established by the Marine Institute Act, 1991; and
- (e) Teagasc—The Agriculture and Food Development Authority, established by section 3 of the Agriculture (Research, Training and Advice) Act, 1988;

"publicly funded artistic work" means an artistic work funded for wholly or mainly artistic purposes by a public artistic funding body;

"qualifying performance" has the meaning assigned to it in section 288 of the Act of 2000;

"Regulations of 2021" means the European Union (Open Data and Re-use of Public Sector Information) Regulations 2021 (S.I. No. 376/2021);

"research" has the meaning assigned to it in section 2 of the Research and Innovation Act 2024, and subsection (2) of that section shall apply;

"work" has the meaning assigned to it in section 2 of the Act of 2000, and includes—

- (a) a creator's artistic work, and
- (b) a performer's qualifying performance.

- (2) (a) In this Act, unless the context otherwise requires, "senior officer"—
 - (i) in the case of a university to which the Act of 1997 applies, shall be construed according to the meaning assigned to "officer" in section 2 of that Act,

- (ii) in the case of any other education provider, higher education provider, or public body, company, institution, organisation or provider referred to in section 36(1) of the Act of 2004, shall be construed by analogy with subparagraph (i),
 - (iii) in the case of any other company to which the Companies Act 2014 applies, shall be construed according to the meaning assigned to "director" in section 2 of that Act, and
 - (iv) in the case of any other body, charity, company, institution, or organisation, shall be construed by analogy with subparagraph (iii).
 - (b) Employers of authors of research outputs shall appoint a senior officer for the purposes of this Act.
 - (c) Where there is any doubt, dispute or difference as to whether a work constitutes a research output for the purposes of section 42(a), the author shall seek and follow the advice of the senior officer appointed pursuant to this subsection.
- (3) A word or expression used in this Act that is also used in Directive 2001/29/EC, or the Act of 2000, or the Act of 2019, or the Regulations of 2021 has, unless the context otherwise requires, the same meaning in this Act as it has in Directive 2001/29/EC, or the Act of 2000, or the Act of 2019, or the Regulations of 2021, as the case may be.

3. Regulations and orders

- (1) The Minister may by regulations provide for any matter referred to in this Act as prescribed or to be prescribed or for the purpose of enabling any provision of this Act to have full effect.
- (2) Where a provision of this Act requires or authorises the Minister to make regulations, such regulations may—
 - (a) make different provision for different circumstances or cases, classes or types, and
 - (b) contain such incidental, supplementary and consequential provisions as appear to the Minister to be necessary or expedient for the purposes of the regulations.

- (3) Without prejudice to the generality of this section, where the Minister is satisfied that it is indispensable to do so, the Minister may by regulation prescribe any additional—
- (a) qualification to the definition of output provided for in section 2,
 - (b) exclusion provided for in section 5, or
 - (c) exception, limitation or example of an imperative reason of overriding public interest sufficient to justify the postponement of the making available of a research output, provided for in section 6
- provided that any such qualification, exclusion, exception, limitation or imperative reason is consistent with the purpose and substance of section 4.
- (4) Every order (other than an order under section 1(2)) and regulation made under this Act shall be laid before each House of the Oireachtas as soon as may be after the order or regulation is made and, if a resolution annulling the order or regulation is passed by either such House within the next 21 days on which that House has sat after the order or regulation is laid before it, the order or regulation, as the case may be, shall be annulled accordingly but without prejudice to the validity of anything previously done thereunder.

PART II

Research outputs

4. Research outputs.

- (1) (a) For the avoidance of doubt, it is not an infringement of the rights conferred by the Act of 2000 to undertake any act pursuant to this Act.
- (b) In particular, nothing in sections 21, 22 or 23 of the Act of 2000 shall prevent the operation of this section.
- (c) The provisions of this Act shall be without prejudice to the operation of section 23 of the Act of 2000.
- (d) Where an act is required or permitted under this Act, any term or condition in any agreement which purports to prohibit, exclude or restrict that act shall be void.
- (2) (a) Subject to sections 5 and 6, in the case of a research output that—

- (i) is created on and after the date of the coming into operation of this section, and
 - (ii) is publicly funded in whole or in part,

the employer of the author of a research output shall make or cause to make the research output available to the public by means of an open repository.
- (b) In the case of any research output to which paragraph (a) applies, where there is more than one joint author, the employer or employers of any joint author or authors may make or cause to make that research output available to the public by means of an open repository, and this shall be sufficient to discharge the obligation of any other employer pursuant to paragraph (a); provided that this shall not prevent any other employer making or causing to make that output available in like manner.
- (c) In the case of any research output to which paragraph (a) applies, the author or a joint author of the research output, or his or her or their funder or funders, may make or cause to make the research output available to the public by means of an open repository, and this shall be sufficient to discharge the obligation of any employer or employers pursuant to paragraph (a); provided that this shall not prevent any other employer, joint author or funder making that output available in like manner.
- (d) In the case either of any research output to which paragraph (a) does not apply or of any other work, the author or a joint author of the output or work, or his or her or their employer or employers, or his or her or their funder or funders, may make or cause to make the output or work available to the public by means of an open repository.
- (e) Subject to sections 5 and 6, in the case of any research output to which paragraph (a) applies that has been accepted for publication by a publisher but has not already been made available pursuant to this section, then the employer of the author of that research output shall ensure—
 - (i) that the author shall immediately deposit that output in an appropriate open repository, and
 - (ii) that the repository shall make it available or cause it to be made available as soon as practicable thereafter.

- (3) (a) In the case of any research output to which subsection 2(a) applies, where the author of the research output is self-employed, then the author shall make or cause to make the output or work available to the public by means of an open repository.
- (b) In the case of any research output to which paragraph (a) applies, and where there is more than one joint author, then the employer of any joint author may make or cause to make that research output available to the public by means of an open repository, and this shall be sufficient to discharge the obligation of the author pursuant to paragraph (a); provided that this shall not prevent any other employer making or causing to make that output available in like manner.
- (c) In the case of any research output to which paragraph (a) applies and where there is more than one joint author, and where one or more of the joint authors is self-employed, then any such joint author may make or cause to make the research output available to the public by means of an open repository, and this shall be sufficient to discharge the obligation of the author pursuant to paragraph (a); provided that this shall not prevent any other joint author making that output available in like manner.
- (d) In the case of any research output to which paragraph (a) applies, the author's funder may make or cause to make the research output available to the public by means of an open repository, and this shall be sufficient to discharge the obligation of the author pursuant to paragraph (a); provided that this shall not prevent any other funder or funders making that output available in like manner.
- (e) For the avoidance of doubt, subsection (2)(d) applies to an author who is self-employed.
- (f) Subject to sections 5 and 6, in the case of any research output to which paragraph (a) applies that has been accepted for publication by a publisher but has not already been made available pursuant to this section, then the author of that research output shall—
- (i) immediately deposit that output in an appropriate open repository, and
 - (ii) insofar as practicable, ensure that the repository shall make it available or cause it to be made available as soon as possible thereafter.

- (4) Research outputs or other works made available pursuant to this section may be used or reused for any lawful purpose.
- (5) Research outputs or other works made available pursuant to this section shall be—
 - (i) assigned a digital object identifier or other suitable persistent identifier, and
 - (ii) provided with metadata.
- (6) Research outputs or other works made available pursuant to this section, and the associated metadata in such outputs and works, shall—
 - (a) be interoperable,
 - (b) be made available in an open format that complies with paragraph (1) of Regulation 7 of the Regulations of 2001, and
 - (c) be made available pursuant to a suitable open public licence, which shall, where practicable and appropriate, be the standard licence published from time to time by the Minister pursuant to paragraph (4) of Regulation 10 of the Regulations of 2001.
- (7) Research outputs or other works made available pursuant to this section shall, where practicable, comply with section 104B(2) of the Act of 2000 (as inserted by section 27 of the 2019 Act).
- (8) The use and re-use of research outputs or other works made available pursuant to this section shall—
 - (a) be free of charge, and
 - (b) not be subject to conditions unless the conditions are in accordance with paragraphs (2) and (3) of Regulation 10 of the Regulations of 2001.
- (9) Where a research output or other work has been made available pursuant to this section, nothing in the Act shall prevent an author, employer, funder or repository from also making that output or work available in any other location.
- (10)
 - (a) Where a research output or other work has been made available pursuant to this section, it shall not be withdrawn from the repository
 - (b) A repository that is being shut down shall seek to export its contents to another open repository.

- (c) Where access to the repository is permanently unavailable, such as where the repository ceases to exist, and where the repository has not exported its contents to another open repository, then the person who, or the body that, had deposited the output or work in the repository shall make or cause to make it available to the public by means of another open repository.
- (11) Where a research output or other work has been made available pursuant to this section, or used and re-used thereafter, it shall be accompanied by a sufficient acknowledgement of the author and the repository, as well as, where practicable and relevant, the location of its first publication by a publisher.

5. Exclusion of publicly funded artistic works.

- (1) A publicly funded artistic work shall not constitute a research output for the purposes of section 4 by reason only of the fact that work is publicly funded in whole or in part.
- (2) A publicly funded artistic work shall not constitute a research output for the purposes of section 4 by reason only of the fact that the work was created in—
 - (a) a university to which the Act of 1997 applies,
 - (b) an education provider or a higher education provider, or
 - (c) a public body, company, institution, organisation or provider referred to in section 36(1) of the Act of 2004.
- (3) A publicly funded artistic work that is not intended by its funder or author to constitute a research output shall not constitute a research output for the purposes of section 4.
- (4) A publicly funded artistic work that is not a research output may be made available by its author pursuant to section 4(2)(d) or section 4(3)(e).
- (5) For the avoidance of doubt, a publicly funded artistic work that is a research output which—
 - (a) has been publicly funded in whole or in part, and
 - (b) is intended by its funder or author to constitute a research output,shall be made available pursuant to section 4 unless section 6 applies.

6. Exceptions, limitations and postponements.

- (1) (a) By way of exception to section 4, that section shall not apply to any research output or other work access to which, or the publication of

which, is excluded or prohibited under any rule of law or enactment other than the Act of 2000.

- (b) In particular, section 4 shall not apply to any research output or other work that—
 - (i) must be kept confidential to ensure that it is not a prejudicial disclosure for the purposes of sections 11 and 12 of the Patents Act, 1992, or
 - (ii) amounts to a trade secret at common law, or in equity, or for the purposes of Article 2(1) of EU Directive 2016/943 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 8 June 2016 on the protection of undisclosed know-how and business information (trade secrets) against their unlawful acquisition, use and disclosure (OJ L 157, 15.6.2016, p. 1–18) and the European Union (Protection of Trade Secrets) Regulations 2018 (S.I. No. 188/2018).

- (2) (a) By way of limitation upon section 4, that section shall not apply to any research output or other work which consists, in whole or in part, of material in respect of which a third party holds intellectual property rights—
 - (i) where an exception or limitation to those rights does not apply, and
 - (ii) for which a license could not practicably be obtained at a reasonable cost.
- (b) Subsection (a) shall not apply where the intellectual property rights held by the third party derive from publicly funded research upon which the research output is based, including where such a third party is—
 - (i) the author's employer,
 - (ii) another employee of the author's employer,
 - (iii) a joint author, or
 - (iv) a public research funding body that has funded, in whole or in part, the research from which the intellectual property rights derive.

- (3) (a) By way of postponement of the making available of a research output, an author who, pursuant to section 4(2), is depositing a research output in an open repository, may apply to the senior officer appointed pursuant to section 2(2) to postpone the making

available by the repository of that output, on the grounds that an imperative reason of overriding public interest requires such a postponement.

- (b) Where the author has demonstrated, with convincing evidence, to the satisfaction of the senior officer, that an imperative reason of overriding public interest has been made out, the making available of the relevant research output may be postponed.
- (c) The senior officer shall ensure that the research output shall be made available as soon as practicable after the imperative reason of overriding public interest shall have ceased to apply.
- (d) By way of postponement of the making available of a research output, an author who, pursuant to section 4(3), is depositing a research output in an open repository, may request that the repository postpone the making available of that output, on the grounds that an imperative reason of overriding public interest requires such a postponement; and the repository shall designate a senior member of its staff to consider this request.
- (e) Where the author has demonstrated, with convincing evidence, to the satisfaction of the senior member of the staff of the repository, that an imperative reason of overriding public interest has been made out, the making available of the relevant research output may be postponed, but only for so long as is strictly necessary to satisfy that reason.
- (f) The senior member of the staff of the repository shall ensure that the research output shall be made available as soon as practicable after the imperative reason of overriding public interest shall have ceased to apply.
- (g) Where, pursuant to this subsection, the making available of a research output is postponed, the repository shall, insofar as practicable, make available the assigned digital object identifier or other persistent identifier and associated metadata.
- (h) For the purposes of this subsection, imperative reasons of overriding public interest include—
 - (i) the clear existence of a serious risk to national security or public order, to the life or health of an individual, or to the environment,
 - (ii) the academic freedom of higher education providers and of academic staff in those providers,

- (iii) the cogent ethical obligations, or the compelling academic interests, of the author,
 - (iv) the necessity for the author to take into account the cogent ethical obligations, or the compelling academic interests, of a co-author,
 - (v) the responsibility of the author to consider the weighty concerns of a funder,
 - (vi) the achievement of the necessary aims of a specific research project which has not been substantially completed,
 - (vii) the paramount need to supplement, or to make further use of, research results,
 - (vii) the protection of commercially sensitive information,
 - (ix) the applicability of relevant national or European Union policies, and
 - (x) the exceptional nature of a significant and sizeable research output, such as a monograph or textbook or other similar long-form work, or a very large website or database or other similar electronic resource.
- (i) For the purposes of this subsection, imperative reasons of overriding public interest shall not include—
- (i) any term or condition in any agreement which is void pursuant to section 4(1)(d),
 - (ii) commercial interests other than those provided for in section 6(1)(b) and section 6(3)(h)(vii), and
 - (iii) the fact that the author objects to the principle of open access.
- (j) For the purposes of this subsection, imperative reasons of overriding public interest shall not apply in circumstances where—
- (i) the relevant research output has previously been made substantially available or otherwise substantially communicated to the public,
 - (ii) information of substantially the same kind as that contained in the relevant research output has previously been made substantially available or otherwise substantially communicated to the public, or
 - (iii) in the opinion of the senior officer appointed pursuant to section 2(2), or of the senior member of the staff of the repository, as the case may be, the public interest would, on balance, be better served by declining rather than granting the

application or request for a postponement of the making available of the relevant research output.

7. Amendment of section 288 of the Act of 2000.

Section 288 of the Act of 2000 is amended by inserting after "*Part VI*" the following: "and the Research Outputs and Open Access Act 2024".

PART III

Oversight, compliance and enforcement

8. Oversight.

- (1) The achievement of the obligations and entitlements set out in section 4 shall constitute a national policy or objective with regard to higher education and research for the purposes of section 35(4)(b) of the Act of 2022.
- (2) An tÚdarás um Ard-Oideachas may, pursuant to section 143 of the Act of 2022, prepare or adopt and issue guidelines, codes or policies to ensure the achievement of the obligations and entitlements set out in section 4.

9. Compliance.

- (1) Having regard to the objects of Taighde Éireann, pursuant to section 8 of the Act of 2024, to promote and support the contribution made by research and innovation and to strengthen the engagement of the research and innovation system with society, the Agency may—
 - (a) in putting in place a scheme for the funding of research and innovation pursuant to section 35 of the Act of 2024, specify that, as a condition of funding, recipients shall ensure the full achievement of the obligations and entitlements set out in section 4,
 - (b) in considering an application for funding invited pursuant to section 36 of the Act of 2024, consider the extent to which applicants have—
 - (i) in the past ensured the achievement of the obligations and entitlements set out in section 4, and
 - (ii) explained in their applications how they intend to ensure the full achievement of the obligations and entitlements set out in section 4 in respect of research outputs from the research and innovation for which the funding may be awarded,

- (c) in making an award of funding pursuant to section 37 of the Act of 2024, specify that ensuring the full achievement of the obligations and entitlements set out in section 4 shall be a condition of the award for the purposes of section 37(9)(i) of the Act of 2024, and
 - (d) otherwise promote the achievement of the obligations and entitlements set out in section 4.
- (2) Where, pursuant to subsection (1), the achievement of the obligations and entitlements set out in section 4 has been made a condition of an award of funding, then the Agency may require that the recipient of funding provide reports on the compliance by the recipient with such a condition, and sections 40 to 46 of the Act of 2024 shall apply.
- (3) A public research funding body may—
 - (a) specify that, as a condition of funding, recipients shall ensure the full achievement of the obligations and entitlements set out in section 4,
 - (b) in considering an application for funding, consider the extent to which applicants have—
 - (i) in the past ensured the achievement of the obligations and entitlements set out in section 4, and
 - (ii) explained in their applications how they intend to ensure the full achievement of the obligations and entitlements set out in section 4 in respect of research outputs from the research for which the funding may be awarded,
 - (c) in making an award of funding, specify that ensuring the full achievement of the obligations and entitlements set out in section 4 shall be a condition of the award, and
 - (d) otherwise promote the achievement of the obligations and entitlements set out in section 4.
- (4) Where, pursuant to subsection (3), the achievement of the obligations and entitlements set out in section 4 has been made a condition of an award of funding (in this subsection referred to as "the condition"), then the public research funding body may—
 - (a) require that the recipient of funding provide reports on the compliance by the recipient with the condition,
 - (b) assess the information (if any) provided by the recipient under this section,

- (c) arrange for an investigation of the matter to be undertaken if there appear to be serious deficiencies regarding compliance by the recipient with the condition,
 - (d) determine whether serious deficiencies regarding compliance by the recipient with the condition have been established, and
 - (e) where such serious deficiencies have been established, impose a sanction proportionate to the deficiencies, including any or some or all of the following—
 - (i) the amendment of the conditions of funding,
 - (ii) the suspension the disbursement of funding,
 - (iii) the cancellation of the award of funding, and
 - (iv) the repayment of some or all of the funding already disbursed;
- (5) The public research funding body shall administer subsections (3) and (4) in an independent and transparent manner and in accordance with the requirements of natural and constitutional justice and fair procedures.

10. Enforcement.

- (1) Where—
- (a) an employee of any employer mentioned in the relevant Schedule has been adversely affected by a failure of the employer to comply with its obligations pursuant to section 4(2)(a) or section 4(2)(f), and
 - (b) the obligation pursuant to section 4(2)(a) has not otherwise been discharged pursuant to section 4(2)(b), section 4(2)(c) or section 4(2)(f),
- then the employee may make a complaint concerning that failure to the Ombudsman pursuant to section 4(3)(a) of the Act of 1980.
- (2) The Ombudsman may, pursuant to section 4(3)(b) of the Act of 1980, undertake an investigation into the compliance by any body mentioned in the relevant Schedule with its obligations pursuant to section 4(2)(a) or to section 4(2)(f) or to both.
- (3) For the purposes of this section, "the relevant Schedule" is the First Schedule to the Act of 1980 (as amended by Part 1 of the Schedule to the Ombudsman (Amendment) Act, 2012).

- (4) The rights of an employee pursuant to this section are in addition to, and without prejudice to, any other contractual or statutory rights which the employee may have.

Main relevant provisions of legislation to which the Bill refers

Health (Corporate Bodies) Act, 1961

<https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/1961/act/27/section/3/enacted/en/html>

3. Establishment of bodies to provide health services.

- (1) The Minister may from time to time by order (in this Act referred to as an establishment order) establish a body to perform functions in, or in relation to, the provision of a health service or two or more health services.

The Health Research Board (Establishment) Order, 1986 (S.I. No. 279 of 1986)

<https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/1986/si/279/made/en/print>

The Minister for Health, in exercise of the powers conferred on him by sections 3 to 6 of the Health (Corporate Bodies) Act, 1961 (No. 27 of 1961) hereby orders as follows:—

...

2. A body to be known as An Bord Taighde Sláinte or, in the English language, the Health Research Board, is hereby established.

...

4. (1) The functions of the Board are as follows:—
 - (a) to promote, assist, commission or conduct medical research;
 - (b) to promote, assist, commission or conduct such epidemiological research as may appropriately or necessarily be conducted at national level and to assist and support other health agencies in the promotion or conduct of such research;
 - (c) to promote, assist, commission or conduct health research;
 - (d) to promote, assist, commission or conduct health services research;
 - (e) to liaise and co-operate with other research bodies in Ireland or elsewhere in the promotion, commissioning or conduct of relevant research;
 - (f) to undertake such other cognate functions as the Minister may from time to time determine.

...

Marine Institute Act, 1991 (No. 2)

<https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/1991/act/2/enacted/en/html>

3. Establishment of Institute

- (1) On the establishment day there shall stand established a body to be known as Foras na Mara and in the English language as the Marine Institute, and in this Act referred to as “the Institute”, to perform the functions conferred on it by this Act.

...

4. Functions of Institute

- (1) The Institute shall have the following general functions, namely, to undertake, to co-ordinate, to promote and to assist in marine research and development and to provide such services related to marine research and development, that in the opinion of the Institute will promote economic development and create employment and protect the marine environment.
- (2) Without prejudice to the generality of subsection (1) of this section, it shall be the general duty of the Institute—
 - (a) to advise the Minister on policy relating to marine research and development,
 - (b) to carry out policy as may be specified by the Minister on marine research and development,
 - (c) to undertake, develop, promote and market marine research and development services,
 - (d) to promote and assist the improvement, development and application of technical and other processes for the exploitation and development of the marine resource,
 - (e) to collect, maintain and disseminate information relating to marine matters,
 - (f) to co-ordinate and control proposals for marine research and development requiring funding from the Exchequer or from any State owned or controlled body or such other body as the Minister may from time to time direct,
 - (g) to evaluate for the Minister proposals for marine research and development requiring funding from the Exchequer or from any

- State owned or controlled body or such other body as the Minister may from time to time direct, and
- (h) to advise the Minister on proposals for marine research and development requiring funding from the Exchequer or from any State owned or controlled body or such other body as the Minister may from time to time direct.

...

Environmental Protection Agency Act, 1992 (No. 7)

<https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/1992/act/7/enacted/en/print>

19. Establishment of Environmental Protection Agency.

- (1) There shall be a body to be known as An Ghníomhaireacht um Chaomhnú Comhshaoil or, in the English language, the Environmental Protection Agency (in this Act referred to as the Agency) to perform the functions assigned to it by or under this Act.

...

52. Functions generally.

- (1) The functions of the Agency shall, subject to the provisions of this Act, include—

...

- (d) the promotion and co-ordination of environmental research, the provision of assistance and advice in relation to such research and the carrying out, causing to be carried out, or arranging for, such research,

...

71. Environmental research.

- (1) The functions of the Agency in relation to environmental research shall include the matters specified in this section.
- (2) (a) The Agency shall advise the Minister on the need for environmental research and shall, at such intervals as the Minister may specify (or, where for the time being no intervals are specified by the Minister,

- at such intervals as it thinks fit) prepare programmes of such research.
- (b) Programmes under this section shall specify—
 - (i) the subjects in relation to which research is necessary and the objectives of such research,
 - (ii) the manner in which and the persons or bodies by which such research could be carried out,
 - (iii) the estimated cost of particular research projects or operations.
 - (c) Programmes under this section shall be prepared after consultation with such persons or bodies as may be prescribed.
- (3) (a) The Agency shall, from time to time, prepare and publish registers of environmental research projects and operations being carried out, or proposed to be carried out, in the State and which shall be available for inspection by any person free of charge at the Agency's headquarters during office hours.
- (b) The Agency shall, insofar as is practicable, co-ordinate environmental research in the State and, for that purpose, may advise any public authority or any other person or body at the request of such person or body in relation to the allocation of financial support or other facilities for such research.
- (4) The Agency may assist by money or in kind, or by the provision of services and facilities (including the services of staff), any person or body carrying out, or proposing to carry out, environmental research.
- (5) The Agency may carry out, cause to be carried out, or arrange for, environmental research in accordance with a programme prepared under subsection (2).
- (6) The Agency shall, in consultation with the Minister, establish and maintain liaison with the Commission of the European Communities and any other international organisation in relation to programmes of environmental research carried out, promoted, or assisted by the Commission or such other organisation, and shall promote and facilitate, as far as possible, participation in such programmes by persons and bodies in the State.

Health Research Board (Establishment) (Amendment) (No. 3) Order 2007 (S.I. No. 305 of 2007)

<https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/2007/si/305/made/en/print>

The Minister for Health and Children, in exercise of the powers conferred on her by section 3 of the Health Corporate Bodies Act 1961 No. 27 of 1961 as

adapted by the Health (Alteration of Name and Department and Title of Minister) Order, 1997 (SI No 308 of 1997) hereby amends the Health Research Board (Establishment) Order 1986 (SI No. 279 of 1986) as follows:

...

2. The Health Research Board (Establishment) Order 1986 (SI No. 279 of 1986) is hereby amended by –

...

(b) the substitution of the following article for Article 4:

(1) The functions of the board are as follows :–

(a) to promote, assist, commission or conduct health research to improve health and increase the effectiveness of the health services

(b) to maintain, develop or support health information systems for the purposes of research and to provide the evidence for health policy and services

(c) to liaise and co-operate with other research bodies in the State and outside the State in the promotion, commissioning or conduct of relevant research;

...

Ombudsman Act, 1980

<https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/1980/act/26/enacted/en/html>

4. Functions of the Ombudsman.

(1) The Ombudsman shall be independent in the performance of his functions.

(2) Subject to the provisions of this Act, the Ombudsman may investigate any action taken by or on behalf of a Department of State or other person specified in Part I of the First Schedule to this Act (being an action taken in the performance of administrative functions) where, upon having carried out a preliminary examination of the matter, it appears to the Ombudsman—

(a) that the action has or may have adversely affected a person (other than a Department of State or other person specified in the First or Second Schedule to this Act), and

(b) that the action was or may have been—

(i) taken without proper authority,

(ii) taken on irrelevant grounds,

(iii) the result of negligence or carelessness,

- (iv) based on erroneous or incomplete information,
 - (v) improperly discriminatory,
 - (vi) based on an undesirable administrative practice, or
 - (vii) otherwise contrary to fair or sound administration.
- (3) The Ombudsman shall not investigate an action unless—
- (a) a complaint has been made to him in relation to the action by a person (other than a Department of State or other person specified in the First or Second Schedule to this Act), or
 - (b) it appears to him, having regard to all the circumstances, that an investigation under this section into the action would be warranted.

...

Agriculture (Research, Training and Advice) Act, 1988

<https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/1988/act/18/enacted/en/html>

3. Establishment of Teagasc—The Agriculture and Food Development Authority.

- (1) On the establishment day there shall stand established a body to be known as Teagasc—The Agriculture and Food Development Authority, and in this Act referred to as “Teagasc”, to perform the functions conferred on it by this Act.

...

4. Functions of Teagasc

- (1) The principal functions of Teagasc shall be—

...

- (c) to undertake, promote, encourage, assist, co-ordinate, facilitate and review, agricultural research and development (including research and development in relation to food processing and the food processing industry).

...

Patents Act, 1992

<https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/1992/act/1/enacted/en/html>

11. Novelty.

- (1) An invention shall be considered to be new if it does not form part of the state of the art.

- (2) The state of the art shall be held to comprise everything made available to the public (whether in the State or elsewhere) by means of a written or oral description, by use, or in any other way, before the date of filing of the patent application.
- (3) Additionally, the content of a patent application as filed, of which the date of filing is prior to the date referred to in subsection (2) and which was published under this Act on or after that date, shall be considered as comprised in the state of the art.
- (4) The provisions of subsections (1), (2) and (3) shall not exclude the patentability of any substance or composition, comprised in the state of the art, for use in a method referred to in subsection (4) of section 9 provided that its use for any method referred to in the said subsection (4) is not comprised in the state of the art.

12. Non-prejudicial disclosures.

- (1) For the application of section 11 a disclosure of the invention shall not be taken into consideration if it occurred not earlier than six months preceding the filing of the patent application and if it was due to, or in consequence of—
 - (a) a breach of confidence or agreement in relation to, or the unlawful obtaining of the matter constituting, the invention, or
 - (b) the fact that the applicant or his legal predecessor has displayed the invention at an international exhibition which is either official or officially recognised under the Convention on International Exhibitions signed at Paris on the 22nd day of November, 1928, or any subsequent treaty, convention or other agreement replacing that Convention:
Provided that the exhibitor states, when making the patent application, that the invention has been so displayed and files a supporting certificate within the period and under the conditions prescribed.
- (2) The Minister may for the purpose of subsection (1) prescribe a period other than the six months specified in that subsection and circumstances other than those specified in paragraph (a) or (b) of that subsection where the Minister is satisfied that it is necessary to do so in order to give effect to any treaty or international convention to which the State is or becomes a party and the said subsection shall be construed accordingly.
- (3) Where a statement appears in the Journal stating that an international exhibition specified in the statement is or was an international exhibition of the class referred to in subsection (1), then for the purposes of this

section the statement shall be evidence that the international exhibition specified therein is or was an international exhibition of such class.

British-Irish Agreement Act, 1999

<https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/1999/act/1/enacted/en/index.html>

**CUID VI
An Foras Teanga**

...

26. Stádas an Fhorais.

- (1) Sa Chuid seo, gairtear “an Foras” den chomhlacht forfheidhmithe le haghaidh teanga a bhunaítear leis an gComhaontú agus ar a dtugtar i mBéarla “The North/South Language Body” nó i nGaeilge “An Foras Teanga” nó in Ultais “Tha Boord o Leid”.

26. Status of Body.

- (1) The implementation body for language established by the Agreement and known in the English language as The North/South Language Body or in the Irish language as An Foras Teanga or in Ullans as Tha Boord o Leid is referred to in this Part as “the Body”.

SCHEDULE

**Agreement Between The Government Of Ireland And The Government Of
The United Kingdom Of Great Britain And Northern Ireland Establishing
Implementation Bodies [the Good Friday Agreement]**

ARTICLE 1

Under and in furtherance of Article 2 of the British-Irish Agreement the following Bodies are hereby established:

...

- (e) an implementation body for language, to be known as The North/South Language Body, which shall be known in Irish as An Foras Teanga or in Ullans as Tha Boord o Leid;

...

ARTICLE 2

1. The functions of each Body shall be those specified in the relevant part of Annex 1 hereto ...
2. Each Body shall exercise its functions and be structured in accordance with the arrangements set out in the relevant parts of Annex 2 hereto.

ANNEX 1
PART 5
Language

One Body, with two separate parts, with the following functions:

Irish Language

...

- undertaking supportive projects, and grant-aiding bodies and groups as considered necessary;

ANNEX 2
PART 5
Language

EXERCISE OF FUNCTIONS

...

- 1.4 The functions of the Body in relation to the Irish language will be exercised by an Irish language agency of the Body. ... Subject to the agreement of the Body the agency will decide its own title. ...

...

Pursuant to these provisions, on 2 December 1999, the Irish Language Body/An Foras Teanga/Tha Boord o Leid established Foras na Gaeilge as the Irish language agency, to provide funding, grants and schemes to support the Irish language.

[see <https://www.forasnagaeilge.ie>].

Copyright and Related Rights Act, 2000

<https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/2000/act/28/enacted/en/index.html>

2. Interpretation.

...

“work” means a literary, dramatic, musical or artistic work, sound recording, film, broadcast, cable programme, typographical arrangement of a published edition or an original database and includes a computer program ...

...

21. Interpretation of author.

In this Act, “author” means the person who creates a work and includes:

- (a) in the case of a sound recording, the producer;
- (b) in the case of a film, the producer and the principal director;
- (c) in the case of a broadcast, the person making the broadcast or in the case of a broadcast which relays another broadcast by reception and immediate retransmission, without alteration, the person making that other broadcast;
- (d) in the case of a cable programme, the person providing the cable programme service in which the programme is included;
- (e) in the case of a typographical arrangement of a published edition, the publisher;
- (f) in the case of a work which is computer-generated, the person by whom the arrangements necessary for the creation of the work are undertaken;
- (g) in the case of an original database, the individual or group of individuals who made the database; and
- (h) in the case of a photograph, the photographer.

22. Works of joint authorship.

- (1) In this Act, “a work of joint authorship” means a work produced by the collaboration of two or more authors in which the contribution of each author is not distinct from that of the other author or authors.
- (2) A film shall be treated as a work of joint authorship unless the producer and the principal director are the same person.
- (3) A broadcast shall be treated as a work of joint authorship if more than one person makes the broadcast and the contribution of each person is not distinct from that of any of the others involved in making that broadcast.
- (4) References in this Act to the author of a work shall, unless otherwise provided, be construed, in relation to a work of joint authorship, as references to all of the authors of the work.

23. First ownership of copyright.

- (1) The author of a work shall be the first owner of the copyright unless—
 - (a) the work is made by an employee in the course of employment, in which case the employer is the first owner of any copyright in the work, subject to any agreement to the contrary,
 - (b) the work is the subject of Government or Oireachtas copyright,

- (c) the work is the subject of the copyright of a prescribed international organisation, or
- (d) the copyright in the work is conferred on some other person by an enactment.

...

40. Making available right.

- (1) References in this Part to the making available to the public of a work shall be construed as including all or any of the following, namely:
 - (a) making available to the public of copies of the work, by wire or wireless means, in such a way that members of the public may access the work from a place and at a time chosen by them (including the making available of copies of works through the Internet);
 - (b) performing, showing or playing a copy of the work in public;
 - (c) broadcasting a copy of the work;
 - (d) including a copy of the work in a cable programme service;
 - (e) issuing copies of the work to the public;
 - (f) renting copies of the work;
 - (g) lending copies of the work without the payment of remuneration to the owner of the copyright in the work, and references to “lawfully making available to the public” shall mean the undertaking of any of the acts referred to in paragraphs (a) to (g) by or with the licence of the copyright owner.
- (2) References in this Part to the making available to the public of copies of a work shall include the making available to the public of the original of the work.
- (3) Subject to subsection (4), the provision of facilities for enabling the making available to the public of copies of a work shall not of itself constitute an act of making available to the public of copies of the work.
- (4) Without prejudice to subsection (3), where a person who provides facilities referred to in that subsection is notified by the owner of the copyright in the work concerned that those facilities are being used to infringe the copyright in that work and that person fails to remove that infringing material as soon as practicable thereafter that person shall also be liable for the infringement.
- (5) Without prejudice to subsection (4), the Minister may prescribe the form of the notice to be given under that subsection and the form shall specify—

- (a) the name and address of the person claiming to be the owner of the copyright in the work concerned,
 - (b) the grounds that the person requesting the removal of material has for such removal, and
 - (c) a list of the material which is to be removed.
- (6) References in this Part to “performance”, in relation to a work, shall include—
- (a) delivery, in the case of lectures, addresses, speeches and sermons, and
 - (b) any means of presentation of sounds or images, or any combination of sounds or images or representations thereof, including presentation by means of a sound recording, film, broadcast or cable programme of the work.
- (7) Where copyright in a work is infringed by its being performed, played or shown in public, by means of apparatus for receiving sounds, images or data or any combination of sounds, images or data, or the representations thereof, conveyed by any means, the person by whom sounds, images or data or any combination of sounds, images or data, or the representations thereof, are sent shall not be regarded as liable for the infringement and a performer shall not be regarded as liable for the infringement to the extent that the infringement relates to his or her activity as a performer.
- (8) There shall be a right of the owner of copyright to make available to the public copies of a work or to authorise others to do so which shall be known and in this Part referred to as the “making available right”.

104B. Electronic form of relevant work.

- (2) The electronic form of the relevant work shall enable copies of the work to be made—
- (a) without undue difficulty,
 - (b) which are easily navigated, and
 - (c) which are capable of being modified.

(as inserted by section of 27 of the 2019 Act).

205. Making available to public copies of recordings of qualifying performances.

- (1) Subject to subsection (2), a performer has the exclusive right to authorise or prohibit the making available to the public of copies of a recording of

the whole or any substantial part of a qualifying performance and it is immaterial whether the copy is made directly or indirectly.

- (2) Where a copy of a sound recording is—
 - (a) played in public, or
 - (b) included in a broadcast or cable programme service,
the right conferred by this section shall be deemed to be satisfied by the payment of equitable remuneration as specified in section 208.
- (3) A reference in Parts III and IV to the making available to the public of copies of a recording shall include the making available to the public of the original recording of the live performance.
- (4) There shall be a right conferred by this section which shall be known and in Parts III and IV referred to as the “making available right”.
- (5) A reference in Parts III and IV to the making available to the public of copies of a recording of a qualifying performance shall include—
 - (a) making available to the public of copies of a recording, by wire or wireless means, in such a way that members of the public may access the recording from a place and at a time individually chosen by them, including the making available of copies of recordings through the Internet,
 - (b) showing or playing a copy of the recording in public,
 - (c) broadcasting a copy of the recording,
 - (d) including a copy of the recording in a cable programme service,
 - (e) issuing copies of the recording to the public,
 - (f) renting copies of the recording, or
 - (g) lending copies of the recording without the payment of remuneration to the rightsowner.
- (6) The making available right is infringed by a person who, without the consent of the performer, undertakes or authorises another to undertake any of the acts referred to in subsection (5).
- (7) Subject to subsection (8), the provision of facilities for enabling the making available to the public of copies of a recording of a performance shall not of itself constitute an act of making available to the public of copies of the recording.
- (8) Without prejudice to subsection (7), where a person who provides facilities referred to in that subsection is notified by the rightsowner that those facilities are being used to infringe any of the rights conferred by Parts III and IV and that person fails to remove that infringing material as

soon as is practicable thereafter, that person shall also be liable for the infringement.

- (9) Without prejudice to subsection (8), the Minister may prescribe the form of the notice to be given under that subsection and the form shall specify—
- (a) the name and address of the person claiming to be the owner of the rights in the recording concerned,
 - (b) the grounds that the person requesting the removal of material has for such removal, and
 - (c) a list of the material which is to be removed.
- (10) Where the making available right is infringed by a copy of a recording being played or shown in public, by means of apparatus for receiving sounds, images or data or any combination of sounds, images or data, or the representations thereof, conveyed by any means, the person by whom sounds, images or data or any combination of sounds, images or data, or the representation thereof, are sent shall not be regarded as liable for the infringement.

288. Qualifying performance.

A performance is a qualifying performance for the purposes of the provisions of this Part and *Part IV* if it is given by a qualifying individual or a qualifying person, or takes place in a qualifying country, territory, state or area, in accordance with this Chapter.

[This is the section as it currently appears. It will be amended by section 4 of the Bill to accommodate the definition of "work" in section 2 of the Bill on which the definition of research "output" is constructed, and it will then provide as follows:

288. Qualifying performance.

A performance is a qualifying performance for the purposes of the provisions of this Part and *Part IV* and the Copyright and Related Rights (Research Outputs and Open Access) Act 2024 if it is given by a qualifying individual or a qualifying person, or takes place in a qualifying country, territory, state or area, in accordance with this Chapter.]

Directive 2001/29/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 May 2001 on the harmonisation of certain aspects of copyright and related rights in the information society

(OJ L 167, 22.6.2001, p. 10–19)

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2001/29/oj>

Article 3

**Right of communication to the public of works
and right of making available to the public other subject-matter**

1. Member States shall provide authors with the exclusive right to authorise or prohibit any communication to the public of their works, by wire or wireless means, including the making available to the public of their works in such a way that members of the public may access them from a place and at a time individually chosen by them.
2. Member States shall provide for the exclusive right to authorise or prohibit the making available to the public, by wire or wireless means, in such a way that members of the public may access them from a place and at a time individually chosen by them:
 - (a) for performers, of fixations of their performances;
 - (b) for phonogram producers, of their phonograms;
 - (c) for the producers of the first fixations of films, of the original and copies of their films;
 - (d) for broadcasting organisations, of fixations of their broadcasts, whether these broadcasts are transmitted by wire or over the air, including by cable or satellite.
3. The rights referred to in paragraphs 1 and 2 shall not be exhausted by any act of communication to the public or making available to the public as set out in this Article.

Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage, pursuant to the Meteorological Services, Radiological Protection and Nuclear Safety (Transfer

of Departmental Administration and Ministerial Functions) Order 2002 (S.I. No. 303 of 2002)

<https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/2002/si/303/made/en/print>

4. (1) The functions vested in the Minister for Public Enterprise -
(a) in relation to meteorological services ... and matters connected therewith, and
...
are transferred to the Minister for the Environment and Local Government.

Housing, Planning and Local Government (Alteration of Name of Department and Title of Minister) Order 2020 (S.I. No. 408 of 2020)

<https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/2020/si/408/made/en/print>

2. The name of the Department of State, the present name of which is, in the Irish language, an Roinn Tithíochta, Pleanála agus Rialtais Áitiúil and, in the English language, the Department of Housing, Planning and Local Government, is altered, in the Irish language, to that of an Roinn Tithíochta, Rialtais Áitiúil agus Oidhreachta and, in the English language, to that of the Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage.

Arts Act, 2003

<https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/2003/act/24/enacted/en/html>

2. Interpretation.

- (1) In this Act—

...
“arts” means any creative or interpretative expression (whether traditional or contemporary) in whatever form, and includes, in particular, visual arts, theatre, literature, music, dance, opera, film, circus and architecture, and includes any medium when used for those purposes;

...

Qualifications and Quality Assurance (Education and Training) Act 2012

<https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/2012/act/28/enacted/en/html>

2. Interpretation.

(1) In this Act—

...

“provider” means a person who provides, organises or procures a programme of education and training;

...

Companies Act 2014

<https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/2014/act/38/enacted/en/html>

2. Interpretation generally

(1) In this Act—

...

“director” includes any person occupying the position of director by whatever name called;

...

Freedom of Information Act 2014

<https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/2014/act/30/enacted/en/html>

36. Commercially sensitive information.

(1) Subject to subsection (2), a head shall refuse to grant an FOI request if the record concerned contains—

- (a) trade secrets of a person other than the requester concerned,
- (b) financial, commercial, scientific or technical or other information whose disclosure could reasonably be expected to result in a material financial loss or gain to the person to whom the information relates, or could prejudice the competitive position of that person in the conduct of his or her profession or business or otherwise in his or her occupation, or
- (c) information whose disclosure could prejudice the conduct or outcome of contractual or other negotiations of the person to whom the information relates.

...

EU Directive 2016/943 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 8 June 2016 on the protection of undisclosed know-how and business information (trade secrets) against their unlawful acquisition, use and disclosure

(OJ L 157, 15.6.2016, p. 1–18)

<http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2016/943/oj>

Article 2
Definitions

For the purposes of this Directive, the following definitions apply:

- (1) ‘trade secret’ means information which meets all of the following requirements:
 - (a) it is secret in the sense that it is not, as a body or in the precise configuration and assembly of its components, generally known among or readily accessible to persons within the circles that normally deal with the kind of information in question;
 - (b) it has commercial value because it is secret;
 - (c) it has been subject to reasonable steps under the circumstances, by the person lawfully in control of the information, to keep it secret;

...

The European Union (Protection of Trade Secrets) Regulations 2018 (S.I. No. 188/2018)

<https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/2018/si/188/>

The European Union (Open Data and Re-use of Public Sector Information) Regulations 2021 (S.I. No. 376/2021)

<https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/2021/si/376/made/en/html>

7. Available formats.

- (1) Where a public sector body or a public undertaking makes a document available for re-use it shall make the document available in any pre-existing format or language, by electronic means where possible and appropriate, in a format that is open, machine-readable, accessible, findable and re-usable, together with its metadata, and the format and metadata shall, where possible, comply with formal open standards.

10. Standard licences.

- (1) Where a public sector body or public undertaking makes documents available for re-use, the re-use of the documents shall not be subject to conditions unless the conditions are in accordance with paragraph (2).
- (2) Any applicable conditions for the re-use of documents shall—
 - (a) be objective, proportionate, non-discriminatory and justified on grounds of an objective of public interest,
 - (b) not unnecessarily restrict possibilities for re-use, and
 - (c) not be used to restrict competition.
- (3) Subject to Regulation 8(8), any applicable conditions for the re-use of documents shall be non-discriminatory for comparable categories of re-use, including for cross-border re-use.
- (4) A public sector body or public undertaking shall, where possible and appropriate, use the standard licence for the re-use of documents published from time to time by the Minister.

A Ministerial Circular provides that the recommended Open Data Licence is **Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY) 4.0**.

[See Department of Public Expenditure and Reform Circular 12/2016 <https://circulars.gov.ie/pdf/circular/per/2016/12.pdf> which does not seem to have been updated after S.I. No. 376/2021.

On Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY) 4.0, see <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/deed.en>].

Higher Education Authority Act 2022

<https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/2022/act/31/enacted/en/html>

2. Interpretation.

- (1) In this Act—

...

“higher education provider” means a person or institution which provides at least one programme of education and training leading to the award of a degree or other qualification which is at least at bachelor degree level and is included within the National Framework of Qualifications;

...

35. Performance framework.

- (1) An tÚdarás shall, with the approval of the Minister, prepare and establish a performance framework for the higher education and research system (in this section referred to as a “performance framework”) at intervals of not less than once every 5 years and may publish the performance framework in such manner as it considers appropriate.

...

- (4) An tÚdarás shall, in preparing a performance framework, have regard to the following:
- (a) the strategy for tertiary education under section 33, taking account of the diversity of functions, objects and priorities of different higher education providers,
 - (b) national policy and objectives with regard to higher education and research, and
 - (c) the matters and outcomes whose implementation is sought to be prioritised.

143. Guidelines, codes and policies.

- (1) An tÚdarás may prepare or adopt and issue guidelines, codes or policies to designated institutions of higher education for any purpose relating to this Act and concerning—
- (a) any matter or thing referred to in this Act or any other enactment, and
 - (b) the implementation of any policy or objective of the Minister or the Government.

...

- (4) An tÚdarás shall send a copy of the guidelines, codes or policies under subsection (1) to the designated institutions of higher education.
- (5) An tÚdarás shall publish the guidelines, codes or policies prepared or adopted by it under this section in such manner as An tÚdarás considers appropriate.

...

The Research and Innovation Act 2024

<https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/2024/act/15/enacted/en/html>

2. Interpretation.

(1) In this Act—

...

“innovation” means the development and use of new ideas, methods, products, processes, policies and services where they have not been used previously;

...

“research” means creative and systematic work in any discipline that is undertaken in order to increase the stock of knowledge (including knowledge of humankind, culture and society) and to devise new applications of available knowledge;

...

8. Objects of Agency.

The Agency shall have regard to the following objects in performing its functions:

- (a) to promote the attainment and maintenance of excellence in the standard and quality of research and innovation undertaken;
- (b) to support the undertaking of research and innovation in all fields of activity and disciplines by researchers with different levels of knowledge, experience and specialist skills in such fields or disciplines;
- (c) to promote and support the contribution made by research and innovation to economic, social, cultural and environmental development and sustainability in the State;
- (d) to strengthen the engagement of the research and innovation system with—
 - (i) the Government, Ministers of the Government and bodies (whether statutory or otherwise) which are funded wholly or partly by public moneys, and
 - (ii) enterprise, non-governmental organisations, cultural institutions and society generally;
- (e) to promote and develop the reputation of the State internationally as a location that is favourable for undertaking research and innovation;
- (f) to advance the principles of equality, diversity and inclusion with regard to opportunities to undertake research and innovation and in the undertaking of that research and innovation.

35. Schemes for funding of research and innovation

- (1) The Agency shall, having regard to—
- (a) the objects of the Agency specified in section 8 , and
 - (b) the functions of the Agency specified in section 9 ,
- put in place a range of schemes for the funding in accordance with this Part of research and innovation to be undertaken in the State and, to the extent provided for in sections 47 and 48, outside the State.

...

- (4) A scheme for the funding of research and innovation referred to in *subsection (1)* that is approved by the Board (in this Act referred to as a “funding scheme”) shall specify the following:

...

- (e) the conditions referred to in section 37(9) to be complied with by a recipient of funding under the scheme;

...

- (6) The Agency shall administer funding schemes in an independent and transparent manner in accordance with their terms and this Part.

...

36. Applications for funding for research and innovation.

- (1) The Agency may invite applications for funding under a funding scheme from all or any of the following:

- (a) a designated institution of higher education;
- (b) a higher education provider that is not a designated institution of higher education;
- (c) an organisation, body or company engaged in research and innovation other than an institution or provider referred to in paragraph (a) or (b);
- (d) any combination of institutions, providers, organisations, bodies and companies referred to in paragraphs (a), (b) and (c).

...

- (4) An application shall be made in accordance with the terms of the funding scheme concerned and this Part.

...

37. Assessment of applications, and awards of funding, for research and innovation

(1) The Chief Executive Officer shall arrange for the assessment, in accordance with subsection (2), of proposals for research and innovation contained in applications received by the Agency pursuant to section 36.

...

(9) The conditions of an award of funding that a recipient of funding under a funding scheme shall comply with (in this Act referred to as the “conditions of funding”) shall include a requirement on the recipient of funding—

(i) to comply with such other conditions as may be determined by the Board.

(10) The Chief Executive Officer shall inform a recipient of funding, by notice in writing, of the terms of the award of funding, including the conditions of funding with which the recipient of funding shall comply.

40. Compliance with conditions of funding for research and innovation

...

41. Information from other bodies relating to awards of funding

...

42. Review of compliance with conditions of funding for research and innovation

...

43. Non-compliance with conditions of funding for research and innovation

...

44. Appeals board

...

45. Determination of appeal by appeals board

...

46. Appeal procedures

...